

The Influence of Psychological Safety on Student Engagement: An Empirical Literature Review

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Abstract: Student engagement is an important aspect in educational performance since it reflects students' investment, motivation, and active engagement in the learning process. Psychological safety is a notion in organizational psychology that relates to how an individual perceives the consequences of taking interpersonal risks in the workplace. However, few academics have investigated psychological safety in education, especially the relationship of psychological safety and student engagement. This report aims to examine empirical papers on the impact of psychological safety on student engagement from 1990 to 2023. Online databases such as Google Scholar, ERIC, Web of Science, and ProQuest were utilized to gather literature. The articles were analyzed using empirical analysis and narrative synthesis, yielding several conclusions. Firstly, there is a positive relationship between psychological safety and student engagement. It is clearly shown that idealized psychologically safe environments have a significant beneficial impact on student engagement. Secondly, a common deficiency among the previous empirical literature is the absence of a strong theoretical explanation. Finally, further research needs focus more on specific aspects of student engagement, and its relationship with students' psychological safety.

Keywords: Psychological Safety, Work Engagement, Student Engagement, Academic Performance, Learning Environment, Empirical Review.

1. Introduction

Student engagement refers to the amount of time and effort a student devotes to learning activities, the degree of engagement and enthusiasm of students in educational activities, which is an important factor affecting learning outcomes and educational success (Gunuc et al., 2022). Numerous obstacles confront higher education, including worldwide educational concerns such as low academic performance, student engagement, and competition (Gandarillas, Elvira-Zorzo & Rodríguez-Vera, 2024). Besides, educational institutions are undergoing several adjustments and developments. Universities endeavor to provide educational opportunities that satisfy the needs of both students and society. However, motivating students to engage in learning is a key challenge for improving educational quality (Teo et al., 2022). More and more individuals recognize that a solid indicator of an institution's excellence is its students' degree of engagement in studying. Student engagement is a reliable

indication of school efficacy since it is related to both immediate and long-term outcomes, as well as academic success (Szabó, Zsolnai, & Fehérvári, 2024). As a result, enhancing student engagement is critical to the growth of higher education and increases institutional talent development standards (Chen, Bian, & Zhu, 2023). Psychological safety is an important part of mental health education. It is a vital aspect of a person's physical and mental health, particularly for teenagers. With the change in social reform and education models, mental health problems have steadily grown more important, particularly the tendency of mental health problems occurring at a younger age, necessitating early intervention (Zou, 2023). As simulation education evolved, a greater emphasis has been placed on creating and sustaining a psychologically secure virtual learning environment. It has been demonstrated that failing to provide psychological safety can result in pupils being incompetent and lacking confidence (Turner et al., 2023). The purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of psychological safety on student engagement to suggest a link between psychological safety and student engagement and provide some suggestions to the educational authorities on the issues of how to improve student engagement by adjusting the psychological safety environment of students.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Psychological Safety

Maslow (1945) first described psychological safety as a sense of confidence, safety, and freedom that is devoid of dread and anxiety, and it includes the belief that a person's current and future needs are met in their hierarchy of needs. Edmondson (1999) used the phrase "team psychological safety" to move psychological safety from the individual to the team level. It's characterized as "when members engage in any risky action in a team, the implementation of these actions is safe, can be accepted by colleagues." Besides, Edmondson acknowledges that psychological safety of team members is strong when: (1) organizational members may talk freely; (2) the organization promotes and permits risk-taking; (3) organizational members trust and respect each other; and (4) organizational members have shared opinions (Edmondson, 1999).

Psychological safety has sparked attention in a variety of disciplines, including healthcare, education, and organizational settings. Newman et al. (2017) identify characteristics that promote psychological safety, such as positive leadership, shared beliefs, supportive organizational settings, interpersonal interactions, and an atmosphere that prioritizes learning over excessive criticism. Forneris et al. (2019) investigated psychological treatments as preventative interventions for Seasonal Affective Disorder, highlighting their role in enhancing mental health. Cornell et al. (2020) examined the past and future of school safety research, distinguishing between physical safety measures and psychological safety therapies to combat peer violence in educational settings. Thyness et al. (2023) discovered that psychological safety was independently connected with students' impression of outstanding learning results during supervised patient visits, emphasising the significance of a supportive environment on learning experience.

2.2 Student Engagement

Astin (1984) defined student engagement as the amount of physical and psychological energy students put into their college experience. With his theory of student involvement, Astin enhanced study into the quality of effort. Astin (1984) claimed that students' scarification of their physical and psychological energy into learning experiences, whether quantitative or qualitative (student-faculty interaction) both inside and outside of their classrooms, determines the amount of learning and personal development that occurs. A highly involved student is one that studies hard, spends a lot of time on campus, is active in student groups, and communicates regularly with instructors and other students (Astin, 1984). Figure 1 depicts the five principles of Student Involvement Theory by Adtin.

Figure 1: Astin's Theory of Involvement. Adapted from Astin (1984).

As defined by Coates and McCormick (2014), student engagement is a broad and complex concept that encompasses student actions, pedagogical techniques, and institutional practices. According to Barkley and Major (2020), student engagement is a mental state throughout a class that reflects their thoughts and emotions. They emphasize that engagement is the junction of motivation and active learning, establishing a strong link between student engagement, learning outcomes, and effective course completion. Wong and Liem (2022) identified two major groups of explanations of student engagement. One example is students actively participating in class activities (also known as learning engagement). The other is student involvement within the school community. (i.e., school involvement). Although both views of student engagement include aspects of student engagement in school-related activities, they differ in terms of the term's essential meaning, object of engagement, and theoretical and historical roots (Wong and Liem, 2022).

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Previous scholars have also expressed a variety of viewpoints on the dimensions of student engagement. Fredericks et al. (2004) recommended defining engagement in three dimensions: behavioral, emotional, and cognitive. Vadenboncoeur (2006) distinguished between formal and informal forms of student engagement, the former referring to in-class settings and the latter to out-of-class activities. Kinzie et al. (2009) categorized student engagement into two dimensions. The first is the amount of time and energy students commit to their schoolwork and other activities that lead to the experiences and products that characterize their academic achievement. The second is the allocation of human and other resources by higher education institutions, as well as the arrangement of learning opportunities and services from which students may benefit from these activities. Figure 2 depicts the three dimensions of student engagement proposed by Fredericks et al..

Figure 2: Engagement framework (adapted from Fredricks et al. (2004))

Several research examined at different factors that lead to improved student engagement. Snijders et al. (2022) investigated the link between student-faculty relationship quality and student engagement, highlighting the significance of pleasant interactions with educational personnel in predicting student engagement and loyalty. Alrajeh et al. (2020) discovered that the interplay of gender and years of experience among math instructors had a substantial impact on student engagement, particularly among female professors. Welmilla (2020) investigated the impact of teachers' emotional intelligence on student engagement and discovered a considerable positive correlation between emotionally intelligent instructors and student engagement. Roopchund (2020) addressed student assistance issues and administrative bureaucracy that influence student engagement and attrition at public universities, suggesting a customer relationship management framework to promote student engagement. Fatawi et al. (2020) investigated the influence of online concept maps on student engagement and learning outcomes, emphasizing the potential benefits of novel teaching approaches for student engagement. Furthermore, Shin and Bolkan (2021) investigated how instructors' intellectually stimulating actions affect student motivation via student engagement, self-efficacy, and academic support, emphasizing the interconnection of these aspects in boosting intrinsic drive to study.

2.3 The Empirical Literature Review of Psychological Safety on Student Engagement

Empirical studies have consistently demonstrated that psychological safety is positively connected with student engagement, which includes aspects such as emotional, behavioral, and cognitive engagement. Kahn (1990) investigated the elements that influence individual engagement and disengagement in diverse environments. He identified three psychological variables required for engagement: meaning, safety, and availability. Psychological safety, in particular, was characterized as the ability to express and use oneself without fear of negatively impacting one's self-image, position, or job. Two qualitative, theory-generating studies of summer camp counselors and members of an architecture firm were undertaken to investigate the settings at work in which people personally engage, or express and exploit their personal selves, and disengage, or retreat and defend their personal selves. Research has found that when employees feel that their work is meaningful, that the work environment is safe and non-threatening, and that they are mentally and physically capable of doing their jobs, they are more likely to commit to their work. Conversely, when these conditions are inadequate, employees tend to psychologically withdraw from work and show lower engagement.

A study by Edmondson (1999) originally focused on teams in organizational settings, but its principles have been applied to educational contexts. In this research, 51 work teams in a manufacturing organization, which measured antecedent, process, and result factors, found that team psychological safety is connected with learning behavior, but team efficacy is not, when team psychological safety is controlled for. It was found that groups with high psychological safety were more likely to engage in open communication, leading to better

learning outcomes. In the classroom, this translates to students being more willing to participate and collaborate, knowing that their contributions are valued.

Tatiana et al. (2022) looked examined the relationship between students' psychological security, academic engagement, and performance. They conducted the examination using the Trustworthiness Factors Survey, Academic Engagement Scale, and academic performance ratings. The sample consisted of 351 students aged 19 to 21 (mean = 19.57, SD = 0.59), with 57% being female. Female students exhibited higher levels of psychological stability, especially when discussing their own ideas in webinar rooms. The same relationship was seen in levels of academic engagement and performance. The linear regression analytic technique demonstrated that psychological safety has a positive impact on academic success. It was possible to conclude that psychological security has a significant influence on students' academic performance and degree of engagement in online learning settings.

Wang et al. (2022) investigated the association between proactive personality, academic self-efficacy, psychological safety, and critical thinking. They also looked at whether academic self-efficacy and psychological safety may moderate the link between proactive personality and critical thinking among Chinese medical students. The cross-sectional study in China took place between October and December 2020. Four Chinese medical universities received a total of 5,920 valid responses. Questionnaires were utilized to assess demographics, academic self-efficacy, psychological safety, proactive personality, and critical thinking. The statistics demonstrate that proactive personality, psychological safety, and academic self-efficacy are important components of critical thinking. Students that study with a better level of psychological safety and academic self-efficacy are more creative in their thinking and hence more engaged in learning.

Thyness et al. (2022) looked examined undergraduate medical students' experiences with clinical supervision, focusing on their activities and interactions. Qualitative study was done using semi-structured interviews with medical students from two English and four Norwegian universities, including transcribed interviews. According to the findings, learning is more likely to occur when students feel safe, take the initiative, seize opportunities to interact, and focus their attention on learning. When students felt uncomfortable, they were more likely to stay silent in the background. The findings show that students who feel psychologically protected are more likely to act and participate during clinical supervision. One technique for promoting psychological safety is to foster relationships between students and supervisors.

Bhargava and Sharma (2023) explored the function of psychological well-being as a mediator of the association between cooperation abilities and student engagement in higher education institutions. The inquiry was conducted using a mixed-methods triangulation style. The data came from final-year students pursuing post-graduation or graduation at India's private colleges. In the primary study, 276 students completed a survey to acquire quantitative data. The findings revealed that students' commitment in their academic program is positively connected with their collaborative abilities. Furthermore, psychological safety has a partial mediation impact on the relationship between student engagement and collaborative capacities.

Thyness et al. (2023) investigated whether European medical students' self-reported excellent learning outcomes during supervised patient interactions were related to supervisor behavior, student engagement and approach, and psychological safety. They conducted a cross-sectional online survey of European medical students, inquiring about their most recent clinical supervision experiences, and then used logistic regression to examine correlations. They observed that the first stage in practice - being engaged, feeling comfortable, and being exposed to what to do (by role modeling and addressing learning goals) - is crucial for students'

views of a positive learning outcome. When kids feel physically safe while studying, they become more engaged in the activity and do better academically.

Table 1: The Empirical Review of Psychological Safety on Student Engagement

Title	Author (year)	Research context	Methodology	Findings
Psychological conditions of personal engagement and disengagement at work.	Kahn (1990)	a summer camp and an architecture firm in US	Qualitative	When employees feel psychologically safe and that they are mentally and physically capable of doing their jobs, they are more likely to engage in their work.
Psychological safety and learning behavior in work teams.	Edmondson (1999)	a manufacturer of office furniture in US	Qualitative	Team psychological safety is connected with learning behavior, but team efficacy is not, when team psychological safety is controlled for.
The relationship between students' psychological security level, academic engagement and performance variables in the digital educational environment.	Tatiana, Kobicheva, Tokareva & Mokhorov(2022)	A university in Russia	Quantitative	Psychological security has a significant influence on students' academic performance and degree of engagement in the online learning environment.
Proactive personality and critical thinking in Chinese medical students: The moderating effects of psychological safety and academic self-efficacy.	Wang, Zhao, Zhang, Yang, ... & Cao, (2022).	Four Chinese medical universities	Quantitative	Students that study with a better level of psychological safety and academic self-efficacy are more creative in their thinking and hence more engaged in learning.
Learning from clinical supervision—a qualitative study of undergraduate medical students' experiences.	Thyness, Steinsbek & Grimstad (2022).	Two English and four Norwegian universities	Qualitative	Learning is more likely to occur when students feel safe, take the initiative, seize opportunities to interact, and focus their attention on learning.
Student engagement through teamwork skills: the mediating role of psychological well-being.	Bhargava & Sharma, (2023).	India's private colleges.	Quantitative	Psychological safety has a partial mediation impact on the relationship between student engagement and collaborative capacities.
What aspects of supervised patient encounters affect students' perception of having an excellent learning outcome? A Survey among European Medical Students.	Thyness, Steinsbek, Andersson, & Grimstad, (2023).	Medical schools from 25 European countries	Quantitative	When students feel physically safe while studying, they become more engaged in the activity and do better academically.

3. Discussion

The preceding overview presents empirical study findings on the impact of psychological safety on engagement, covering both occupational engagement and learning engagement. The study research context primarily focuses on educational institutions from various nations with diverse cultural background. Further discussions will be presented in details in the following section.

Firstly, although research on the relationship of psychological safety and student engagement does exist, study digging into how students' psychological safety relates to the specific aspects of student engagement did not begin over the past few decades. According to Fredericks et al. (2004), engagement can be concluded as behavioral engagement, emotional engagement and cognitive engagement. Figuring out how students' psychological safety affects their different aspects of engagement is significant for further clarifying the relationship between students' psychological state and academic performance in the future.

Second, a common deficiency among the empirical literature previously emphasized is the absence of a novel theoretical explanation. They have a conceptual framework that is comparable, with a focus on determining the validity of presumptions about the relationship between psychological safety and student engagement or work engagement. The empirical investigations described above seldom provide theoretical backing, and the research results are not strong enough.

Lastly, a dearth of empirical research has examined the mediating role that exists between psychological safety and the dependent variables like student engagement, performance and efficiency.

Based on the discussion above, it is advised that future studies concentrate more on the impact of psychological safety on many different aspects of student engagement. Additionally, the explaining mechanism must be creative and innovative when supported by strong theoretical frameworks. To increase awareness of students' psychological problems and learning engagement, additional study from different areas and nations is urged to look into the connection between psychological safety and student engagement.

4. Conclusion

In this empirical review, some research on the influence of psychological safety on student engagement has been compiled and analyzed. It identified that there is a positive relationship between psychological safety and student engagement. It is clearly shown that idealized psychologically safe environments have a significant beneficial impact on student engagement. However, when examining the research theoretical foundation, research context, and research design, the deficiencies in the empirical investigation on influencing student engagement components may be solved by extending supported theory, research context, and research design, respectively. Student engagement is a complex and multi-dimensional concept in education, which has a profound impact on the growth and development of students. Schools should encourage students to actively participate in the educational process by optimizing educational practices and providing rich learning opportunities, so as to achieve the dual improvement of education quality and personal growth of students. This study intends to raise public awareness of student psychological development and student engagement issues, motivate more educational institutions to learn about this connected topic, and inspire researchers to do more research in order to give better answers and interventions.

References

1. Alrajeh, T. S., & Shindel, B. W. (2020). Student Engagement and Math Teachers Support. *Journal on mathematics education*, 11(2), 167-180.
2. Astin, A. W. (1984). "Student Involvement: A Developmental Theory for Higher Education." *Journal of College Student Personnel*.
3. Barkley, E. F., & Major, C. H. (2020). *Student engagement techniques: A handbook for college faculty*. John Wiley & Sons.
4. Bhargava, S., & Sharma, R. (2023). Student engagement through teamwork skills: the mediating role of psychological well-being. *Higher Education, Skills and Work-Based Learning*.
5. Chen, C., Bian, F., & Zhu, Y. (2023). The relationship between social support and academic engagement among university students: the chain mediating effects of life satisfaction and academic motivation. *BMC Public Health*, 23(1), 2368.
6. Coates, H., & McCormick, A. C. (2014). Engaging university students. *International insights from system-wide studies*.
7. Cornell, D. G., Mayer, M. J., & Sulkowski, M. L. (2020). History and future of school safety research. *School psychology review*, 50(2-3), 143-157.
8. Edmondson, A. (1999). Psychological safety and learning behavior in work teams. *Administrative science quarterly*, 44(2), 350-383.
9. Fatawi, I., Degeng, I. N. S., Setyosari, P., Ulfa, S., & Hirashima, T. (2020). Effect of online-based concept map on student engagement and learning outcome. *International Journal of Distance Education Technologies (IJDET)*, 18(3), 42-56.

10. Forneris, C. A., Nussbaumer-Streit, B., Morgan, L. C., Greenblatt, A., Van Noord, M. G., Gaynes, B. N., ... & Gartlehner, G. (2019). Psychological therapies for preventing seasonal affective disorder. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, (5).
11. Fredericks, J.A., Blumenfeld, P.C., & Paris, A.H. (2004). School engagement: Potential of the concept, state of the evidence. *Review of Educational Research*, 74(1), 59-109.
12. Gandarillas, M. A., Elvira-Zorzo, M. N., & Rodríguez-Vera, M. (2024). The impact of parenting practices and family economy on psychological wellbeing and learning patterns in higher education students. *Psicologia: Reflexão e Crítica*, 37, 8.
13. Gunuc, S., Artun, H., Yigit, E., & Keser, H. (2022). Examining the relationship between student engagement and campus climate: A case in Turkey. *Journal of College Student Retention: Research, Theory & Practice*, 23(4), 1099-1119.
14. Kahn, W. A. (1990). Psychological conditions of personal engagement and disengagement at work. *Academy of management journal*, 33(4), 692-724.
15. Maslow A H, Hirsh E, Stein M & Honigmann I. (1945). A clinically derived test for measuring psychological security-insecurity[J]. *Journal of General Psychology*, 33: 21-41.
16. Newman, A., Donohue, R., & Eva, N. (2017). Psychological safety: A systematic review of the literature. *Human resource management review*, 27(3), 521-535.
17. Roopchand, R. (2020). Towards a conceptual framework for customer relationship management for public universities in Mauritius. *International Journal of Electronic Customer Relationship Management*, 12(4), 326-356.
18. Shin, M., & Bolkan, S. (2021). Intellectually stimulating students' intrinsic motivation: the mediating influence of student engagement, self-efficacy, and student academic support. *Communication Education*, 70(2), 146-164.
19. Snijders, I., Wijnia, L., Kuiper, R. M., Rikers, R. M., & Loyens, S. M. (2022). Relationship quality in higher education and the interplay with student engagement and loyalty. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 92(2), 425-446.
20. Szabó, L., Zsolnai, A., & Fehérvári, A. (2024). The relationship between student engagement and dropout risk in early adolescence. *International Journal of Educational Research Open*, 6, 100328.
21. Tatiana, B., Kobicheva, A., Tokareva, E., & Mokhorov, D. (2022). The relationship between students' psychological security level, academic engagement and performance variables in the digital educational environment. *Education and Information Technologies*, 27(7), 9385-9399.
22. Teo, T., Khazaie, S., & Derakhshan, A. (2022). Exploring teacher immediacy-(non) dependency in the tutored augmented reality game-assisted flipped classrooms of English for medical purposes comprehension among the Asian students. *Computers & Education*, 179, 104406.
23. Thyness, C., Steinsbekk, A., & Grimstad, H. (2022). Learning from clinical supervision—a qualitative study of undergraduate medical students' experiences. *Medical Education Online*, 27(1), 2048514.
24. Thyness, C., Steinsbekk, A., Andersson, V., & Grimstad, H. (2023). What aspects of supervised patient encounters affect students' perception of having an excellent learning outcome? A Survey among European Medical Students. *Advances in Medical Education and Practice*, 475-485.

25. Turner, S., Harder, N., Martin, D., & Gillman, L. (2023). Psychological safety in simulation: Perspectives of nursing students and faculty. *Nurse Education Today*, 122, 105712.
26. Vadenboncoeur, J.A. (2006). Engaging young people: Learning in informal contexts. *Review of Research in Education*, 30, 239-278.
27. Wang, Y. P., Zhao, C. X., Zhang, S. E., Li, Q. L., Tian, J., Yang, M. L., ... & Cao, D. P. (2022). Proactive personality and critical thinking in Chinese medical students: The moderating effects of psychological safety and academic self-efficacy. *Frontiers in psychology*, 13, 1003536.
28. Welmilla, I. (2020). Students' perspective on the emotional intelligence of teachers on student engagement. *Int. Bus. Res*, 13(04), 30-43.
29. Wolf-Wendel, L., Ward, K., & Kinzie, J. (2009). A tangled web of terms: The overlap and unique contribution of involvement, engagement, and integration to understanding college student success. *Journal of College Student Development*, 50(4), 407-428.
30. Wong, Z. Y., & Liem, G. A. D. (2022). Student engagement: Current state of the construct, conceptual refinement, and future research directions. *Educational Psychology Review*, 34(1), 107-138.
31. Woreta, G. T. (2024). Predictors of academic engagement of high school students: academic socialization and motivational beliefs. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 15, 1347163.
32. Zou, L.Y. (2023). Put mental health work in a more prominent position. *Chinese Education Journal*, 1(2), 11-12.